

4:00-6:00 PM (2077)

Multidomain Training in Healthy Older Adults Revisited: A Three-Level Meta-Analysis. JENNIFER RIEKER and JOSÉ REALES, *Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia*, MÓNICA MUIÑOS, *Universidad Internacional de Valencia*, SOLEDAD BALLESTEROS, *Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia* – The effectiveness of multidomain training compared to cognitive or physical training alone has been controversial with some studies suggesting that combined interventions might produce synergetic effects. We conducted a three-level meta-analysis on the transfer effects of multidomain interventions versus cognitive and physical training alone. We obtained 1,070 effect sizes from 54 studies, involving 5,547 healthy older adults. Our results revealed a synergetic effect of multidomain training on executive functions, and larger effects on attention and memory than cognitive and physical training. Multidomain and single cognitive training produced similar effects on memory in comparison to physical training. We did not find differences in processing speed, verbal functions, and global cognition. Moderator analyses showed a complex pattern. In general, age, publication year, and study quality were not significant. We conclude that the combination of cognitive training with physical exercise could be a promising strategy to prevent cognitive and physical declines with aging. Email: Soledad Ballesteros, mballesteros@psi.uned.es

4:00-6:00 PM (2078)

Longitudinal Change in Letter and Category Fluency: An Analysis of the Seattle Longitudinal Study. NICHOL CASTRO, *University of Washington & University at Buffalo, SUNY*, PAUL ROBINSON, K. WARNER SCHAIE, THOMAS GRABOWSKI, and SHERRY WILLIS, *University of Washington* – Verbal fluency tasks are commonly given in neuropsychological testing. Many reports show cross-sectional differences between younger and older adults, as well as cognitively normal adults and adults with dementia. To extend prior research, this project examined longitudinal change in two verbal fluency tasks (letter and category) using data from the Seattle Longitudinal Study, a multi-decade, cohort sequential study of community-dwelling adults. There were 854 adults who completed both tasks across several testing occasions. We used multilevel modeling to predict number of unique productions on each task from predictors of time, age, and dementia status, as well as risk factors for dementia, namely high blood pressure and APOE e4. We found a significant interaction of dementia status by time² but no effect of APOE e4 for both tasks, with diverging results regarding high blood pressure and age. We discuss the implications of these results for assessment of verbal fluency performance.

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4:00-6:00 PM (2079)

Before and Beyond the N400: Confirmed and Disconfirmed Lexical Predictions in Aging. SPYRIDOULA CHEIMARIOU, *University of Alabama*, THOMAS FARMER, *California State University*, JEAN GORDON, *University of Iowa* – Older adults exhibit attenuated N400 ERP effects, indicating less efficient use of context than younger adults. Early (N250) and late (P600) ERP components are also sensitive to manipulations of predictability, reflecting early visual effects and prediction cost, respectively. Here, we examined patterns of early- and later-occurring ERP effects to determine the relative time-course of

predictive processing effects in older relative to younger adults. We re-analyzed an existing dataset in which we observed N400 effects in older and younger adults (picture-word matching task), after crossing predictiveness with congruency. Younger adults exhibited N250 effects of predictiveness and congruency whereas these effects were absent in older adults, suggesting that effects associated with the violation of early visual expectations are mitigated in older adults. The P600 effect, however, was larger for older than younger adults, indicating larger misprediction cost for the older group. Our results support findings in the eye-tracking literature demonstrating stronger contextual effects in older adults in later reading measures (e.g., regression-path duration), and may thus reconcile two (often contradictory) lines of experimental research.

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4:00-6:00 PM (2080)

Age Differences in Memory for Socially Important Associations: The Effects of Assigned and Self-Perceived Social Importance and Schematic Support. JULIA SCARINGI, LINGQIAN LI, and LIXIA YANG, *Ryerson University* – Recent study showed that age-related associative memory deficits can be minimized for information depicted as socially important (e.g., Hargis & Castel, 2017). This study aimed to further assess the effects of both arbitrarily assigned and the self-perceived social importance in young and older adults' memory for low-schematic face-name and high-schematic face-occupation associations. Young and older adults studied and recalled 16 face-name-occupation triplets (with neutral expressions) in four blocks, followed by a cued recall of names and occupations at the end. The faces were arbitrarily cued as socially important (i.e., future personal interactions, with an orange frame) or unimportant (i.e., no future personal interaction, without a frame). Finally, they rated all the triplets for their self-perceived social importance on a 10-point Likert Scale. The results showed that the self-perceived, but not the arbitrarily assigned, social importance reduced older adults' associative memory deficits, specifically for the high-schematic face-occupation pairs. This suggests that the combination of schematic support and self-perceived social value can effectively mitigate older adults' associative memory deficit.

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4:00-6:00 PM (2081)

Gender Differences in Thematic Content Analysis of Autobiographical Memory in Life Review from the Perspective of Cognitive Aging. AYA HOSOKAWA, *Aino University* – Life review consists of autobiographical memory including momentous self-related memory across the lifespan. Our previous study examining effects of group reminiscence on cognitive aging found that regular participation in group life review improved performances on memory and cognition. The purpose of the current study was to focus on thematic content analysis of life narratives to explore how autobiographical memories were represented in life review. Forty old adults including 20 females shared autobiographical narrative in each life stage during life review group sessions. Depictions in each transcript from voice data recognized as non-autobiographical memory were in advance eliminated from analysis. Each unit of autobiographical narrative was labeled according to topic sentence to categorize into two dimensional table of life stage and topic. Female participants were more likely to focus on family-related events while male participants were